

Research paper

Challenges for carbon crediting in *Zostera marina* (eelgrass) meadowsHilary Kennedy^a, Carmen Leiva-Dueñas^b, Catherine E. Lovelock^c, Dorte Krause-Jensen^{b,*}^a School of Ocean Sciences, Bangor University, Anglesey, Wales, United Kingdom^b Aarhus University, Department of Ecoscience, Aarhus, Denmark^c School of Environment, The University of Queensland, St Lucia, Queensland, Australia

HIGHLIGHTS

- The scope for carbon market projects with eelgrass is limited.
- Restoration of eelgrass meadows make modest contribution to climate change mitigation.
- The multiple additional benefits of eelgrass meadows should be considered.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

The protection and restoration of seagrass meadows are recognised contributions to address the combined biodiversity-climate crises because the meadows are hotspots of biodiversity, sediment organic carbon (OC) stocks and carbon accumulation rate (CAR) and have experienced major global declines in response to pressures. However, OC storage varies among seagrass species. Here we assess carbon storage and CAR in meadows of *Zostera marina* (eelgrass), the most widely distributed seagrass species, thereby evaluating their potential for inclusion in carbon markets. We review sediment OC stocks, CAR, sources and stability (mineral associated organic matter - MAOM) of the organic matter. We compare our findings for eelgrass, which is a fast-growing colonizing-opportunistic seagrass species, with those for *Posidonia oceanica*, typifying slow-growing, persistent seagrass species. Eelgrass sediment OC stocks and CAR display median stocks 40 % and 50 % lower, respectively, than those of *P. oceanica* and median eelgrass CAR is only 21 % of the Tier 1 emission factor for seagrass used in the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) greenhouse gas accounting guidelines. The OC stocks in most (60%) vegetated areas were not significantly different from stocks of nearby unvegetated sediments and only 27 % of the eelgrass sediment samples in this compilation would return positive OC values after subtracting the MAOM fraction, a requirement of some carbon market methodologies. These features may partly be due to the strong spatial heterogeneity and temporal dynamics of eelgrass meadows, eelgrass traits as well as export of

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eelgrass carbon beyond the meadows. We discuss implications for carbon market restoration projects and encourage considering all the ecosystem services the meadows provide.

1. Introduction

The large areal extent and widespread distribution of seagrass meadows alongside the range of ecosystem services they provide make them globally important ecosystems (Lima et al., 2023). Their global distribution, carbon accumulation rate (CAR) and long-term storage of the sequestered carbon has directed the attention towards their sustainable management for climate change mitigation (Fourqurean et al., 2012), given the major losses they have experienced (Waycott et al., 2009; Arias-Ortiz et al., 2018a). The loss of seagrass meadows can potentially lead to GHG emissions (Lovelock et al., 2017), while their restoration can lead to GHG removals (Oreska et al., 2020), thus contributing either to climate change or support its mitigation.

The loss of seagrass meadows has been estimated to be 29 % of areal extent since 1879 (Waycott et al., 2009), and although loss rates have recently decreased in some regions (de los Santos et al., 2019), overall loss rates of <2 % per year are still evident (Dunic et al., 2021). Better protection is therefore urgently needed, and seagrass restoration can support redressing the loss and reinstating the climate change mitigation potential of seagrass meadows where stressors have been controlled (Marbà et al., 2015; Oreska et al., 2020; Flindt et al., 2024).

As a consequence, vegetated coastal wetlands such as seagrass meadows, alongside mangrove and tidal marshes, have become recognised as natural climate solutions in national and international policy. The 2013 Supplement to the 2006 Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas (GHG) Inventories: Wetlands (IPCC, 2014) provides guidance for countries to report GHG emissions and removals resulting from coastal wetland land-use changes. Additionally, a range of nations have included coastal wetlands in their mitigation activities as part of their National Determined Contributions (Herr and Landis, 2016). Alongside these policies, voluntary carbon markets have been developed to credit actions in reducing GHG emissions (Van der Gaast and Spijker, 2013; Van der Gaast et al., 2018). So far, however, there has been limited evidence of seagrass meadow restoration being included in voluntary market projects. For example, Australia, France and Japan have produced national methodologies for carbon credits that include seagrass (Lovelock et al., 2023; Kuwae et al., 2022; Comte et al., 2024). VERRA and Plan Vivo are among the organisations that approve voluntary carbon offset methodologies and certify and register projects; a seagrass restoration project is being developed in the USA (Oreska et al., 2020) using VERRA methodology and Plan Vivo are considering seagrass meadows under their proposed climate contribution and biodiversity credits.

While the global potential for the restoration of seagrass meadows to mitigate climate change has attracted considerable attention, there has not been the same focus on the capacity of individual seagrass genera to provide these benefits. Nevertheless, seagrass traits have, in addition to geomorphic setting, been identified as key drivers of sediment OC stocks leading to differences between long-lived genera like *Posidonia* sp. and short-lived genera like *Zostera* sp. (Kennedy et al., 2022). Here we address the knowledge gap on individual species' mitigation potential by examining the capacity of *Zostera marina* (eelgrass) and *Posidonia oceanica* to contribute to climate change mitigation and get recognition of successful restoration through voluntary carbon market methodologies.

Eelgrass is, by far, the globally most widespread seagrass species, occurring in Pacific and Atlantic areas of the Northern Hemisphere from warm temperate to Arctic environments (Green and Short, 2003), spanning 40° of latitude and a range of ~18°C in average annual temperatures (Yu et al., 2023). Its current areal extent is a fraction of that recorded historically in the North Atlantic Ocean due to the “wasting disease” that resulted in the loss of possibly 90 % of eelgrass in the 1930s

(Sullivan et al., 2013). Although some recovery took place, anthropogenic disturbances have caused additional losses of eelgrass e.g. in Europe (Boström et al., 2014; de los Santos et al., 2019; Krause-Jensen et al., 2021). *Posidonia oceanica* is endemic to the Mediterranean, spanning around 10 degrees of latitude, and a strong temperature gradient from west to east. *Posidonia oceanica* has also suffered significant losses of around 34 % in the last 50 years due to direct and indirect anthropogenic activities (de los Santos et al., 2019). It is a protected species in the EU subjected to several direct regulations (EC Habitat Directive (92/43/EEC), Barcelona Convention, Bern Convention; Boudouresque et al., 2012) and a defined habitat in the Natura 2000 network, whereas eelgrass is not a defined habitat under the Natura 2000 network.

We use these two contrasting seagrass species to compare the opportunity and barriers to their potential inclusion in carbon markets. While eelgrass meadows represent fast-growing colonizing-opportunistic seagrass species, *P. oceanica*, typifies slow-growing, persistent seagrass species. Using published data, we review the scientific evidence that can be used to support carbon projects. We have collated data on sediment OC stocks and CAR, estimates of carbon sources and meadow dynamics to better understand the potential for restoration of eelgrass and *P. oceanica* and their inclusion under methods available in voluntary carbon markets. We also indicate that climate change mitigation is only one of the ecosystem services that seagrass meadows provide and advocate for the other services to be better recognised and valued.

2. Methods

2.1. Data compilation

We extracted data on eelgrass sediment OC stocks inside meadows and where possible, paired values of OC stocks outside eelgrass meadows, CAR in sediments (only in vegetated areas), carbon stable isotopic composition of seagrass and sediment as well as that of OC and organic matter (OM) content to indicate autochthonous and allochthonous OC content. Where data was available, we compared values between eelgrass and *Posidonia oceanica* meadows to highlight how differences in traits between seagrass species can lead to different contributions to climate change mitigation. The majority of data were from earlier compilations of seagrass blue carbon data (e.g., Arias Ortiz, 2019; Prentice et al., 2020; Kennedy et al., 2022; Röhr et al., 2016, 2018; Leiva-Dueñas et al., 2023; Graversen et al., 2024).

To evaluate sediment OC stocks in eelgrass and *P. oceanica* meadows, only cores with lengths of at least between 20 and 25 cm were considered. For comparability, stocks were recalculated to provide the OC stock to 25 cm depth. To encompass spatial variability, replicate cores and individual site cores were included and average site core data was only used when that was the extent of the data available. For the comparison between vegetated and unvegetated sediment OC stocks, only paired data was used, regardless of the criteria used to define areas outside meadows or the sediment depth used. In this comparison data from OC stocks were derived from cores of 5 to 50 cm depth. Core length was considered in later statistical analysis to ensure no bias (see data analysis section).

Sediment CAR was predominantly measured by the ²¹⁰Pb dating technique, but cores from *P. oceanica* meadows in Greece (Apostolaki et al., 2024) were dated with ¹⁴C. To ensure comparability between the ¹⁴C-derived CAR and ²¹⁰Pb-derived CAR, which can cover vastly different time periods (thousands of years vs. a maximum of 150 years, respectively), the raw data including the dates derived from the ¹⁴C derived age-depth models was used to calculate the ¹⁴C-derived CAR for

the last 100 years. The reported ^{210}Pb derived CAR were used, regardless of the depth or time over which the accumulation rate was determined.

We compared species-specific median values of CAR and OC stocks to the IPCC Tier 1 default for seagrass ecosystems, as this benchmark is widely used in national greenhouse gas inventories and provides a standardized reference for evaluating whether global default values accurately represent species-level variability. We discuss our findings in relation to the dynamic nature of eelgrass meadows based on examples from Danish coastal waters (Frederiksen et al., 2004a, 2004b; Balsby et al., 2017), the UK (Bull et al., 2012), the Netherlands (Valle et al., 2013) and Massachusetts, USA (Schaefer et al., 2025).

In some carbon market blue carbon crediting methodologies, a distinction is made between autochthonous and allochthonous OC. Allochthonous OC, or recalcitrant allochthonous OC in seagrass meadows, is only considered when it would be vulnerable to remineralisation without the restoration activities (Needelman et al., 2018). Currently, there is no standardized method to evaluate autochthonous and allochthonous OC pools or their vulnerability to remineralisation, so proxies are often employed. The stable carbon isotopic composition of OC ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) is used as a proxy (Ward et al., 2024) to discriminate between sediment OC derived from seagrass production (autochthonous) and the OC from plants (or algae) that were produced outside the project area (allochthonous). One conservative approach in carbon market accounting methods is to discount all allochthonous OC, regardless of its vulnerability. In this study, using only data sets with paired values of leaf and surface sediment, the difference in $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ between surface sediment and seagrass leaves ($\Delta^{13}\text{C}$) was used as a simple representation of the allochthonous fraction of the OC, while recognising that abundance and type of allochthonous OC sources will moderate this assumption (Kennedy et al., 2022). In each case, the surface sediment was represented by the top slice of any core. This comparison was supplemented by literature examples where the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of potential OC sources have been used to infer the relative contribution of their OC and eelgrass OC to the sediment OC pools.

Another approach to determine recalcitrant allochthonous OC is to use a proxy (i.e. OC resistant to remineralisation) which is based on the calculation of mineral-protected allochthonous OC (Mayer, 1994; Needelman et al., 2018) as outlined for the Verified Carbon Standard (VCS) VM0033 methodology under the VERRA program. The recalcitrant allochthonous OC is calculated from the mineral-associated organic matter (MAOM). More specifically it is calculated by multiplying the mineral mass proportion of the sample (mass remaining after loss-on-ignition) by a default average value of 1.5 % to represent the MAOM with this value being converted to MAOC using the relationship between OM and OC (Needelman et al., 2018; Verra, 2023) and the resulting value is deducted from the total OC. The default value of 1.5 %, derived from Mayer (1994), represents the mean refractory OC content, with upper and lower bounds (95 % confidence interval: 1.1–2.0 %) calculated from downcore data in open ocean cores. Independent analyses of OM and OC on sediment samples from eelgrass (Röhr et al., 2018; Gagnon et al., 2024) and from *P. oceanica* meadows (Graversen et al., 2024; Mazarrasa et al., 2017) were used to determine the relationships between OM and OC and the recalcitrant allochthonous carbon deduction (as % total OC). This comparison was supplemented by literature examples where the MAOM content and %MAOM of the sediment OC have been directly measured and used to infer the long-term stabilization of OC, although the majority of reported data is from tidal marsh and mangrove ecosystems rather than from seagrass.

Using the global seagrass restoration dataset compiled by van Katwijk et al. (2016), we calculated their semi-quantitative 'integrated success score' (ISS), as indicated in their study, for each seagrass genus. The ISS combined two metrics: a) initial trial survival, scored as 1 if plants were present, or 0 if they had disappeared, during an early monitoring event (≤ 9 months), and b) long-term planting performance, (scored for trials monitored beyond the 22 months) as: 0 = lost, 1 = declined, 2 = stable, or 3 = increased since planting. The ISS was

calculated by multiplying the mean initial trial survival by the mean long-term performance, both averaged per seagrass species category. The standard deviation of the ISS was derived from the standard deviations of the initial survival and long-term performance metrics.

2.2. Statistical analyses

Given the skewed distribution of CAR and OC stock data, the median was chosen as the measure of central tendency. To account for differences in sampling effort among sites, we first calculated the mean CAR and OC stock value for each site and then estimated the median of these site-level means. To assess whether the probability distributions of sediment OC stocks and CARs significantly differ between *P. oceanica* and eelgrass meadows, we used the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K–S) test. We expected different distributions, reflecting different species-specific sedimentary processes influencing CAR and OC storage. We anticipate that *P. oceanica* meadows will display a broader distribution with greater frequency of moderate values and occasional high values reflecting thick, carbon rich sediment deposits (mattes) that are observed, greater plant productivity and lower OC degradation, whereas eelgrass meadows are likely to show narrower right-skewed distributions with fewer high-end outliers. In addition, we used Wilcoxon tests to determine whether median OC stocks and CARs significantly differ between *P. oceanica* and eelgrass meadows, complementing the distributional comparison with an assessment of central tendencies.

A meta-analysis was conducted to quantify differences in sediment OC stocks between vegetated and unvegetated areas. Aggregate study-level differences in sediment OC stocks between vegetated and unvegetated sediments were used to calculate the mean difference (MD) and 95 % confidence intervals. As we anticipated considerable between-study and site heterogeneity, a random-effects model was used to pool effect sizes. The between study and site variance τ^2 was estimated by restricted maximum likelihood, recommended because it yields approximately unbiased heterogeneity estimates. To obtain more reliable confidence intervals for the pooled effect under random effects we used the Hartung–Knapp adjustment. We performed a subgroup analysis based on the sediment thickness used to calculate sediment OC stocks. Pooled effects and heterogeneity were estimated within categories defined by the thickness of the sediment section used to calculate OC stocks: shallow stocks (0–3.5 cm and up to 15 cm), intermediate stocks (0–15 cm and up to 25 cm), and deep stocks (0–25 cm and up to 50 cm), as well as for the overall dataset. To classify the direction of individual site effects, we extracted MD and their 95 % confidence intervals from the meta-analysis. Each site was then categorized based on whether its confidence interval excluded zero: higher OC stock in vegetated areas if the lower bound was >0 , lower OC stock in vegetated areas if the upper bound was <0 and no significant difference if the interval included zero.

All the analyses and visualization were performed with R v. 4.3.0 (R Core Team, 2023).

All data are available in Figshare: <https://figshare.com/s/ea5eda2a92f8311b1e46>.

3. Results

3.1. Eelgrass sediment OC accumulation rate (CAR)

The compiled data sets (Fig. 1A,C) displayed a large range of core-level values from no measurable net accumulation to a maximum of $229 \text{ g OC m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ for eelgrass and a maximum of $116 \text{ g OC m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ for *P. oceanica* meadows. We excluded those cores where no net accumulation could be measured due to intense sediment mixing or erosion ($n = 10$ for eelgrass and $n = 3$ for *P. oceanica*). Eelgrass displayed a pronounced right-skew distribution of site-level CAR, with 75 % of values below $\sim 32 \text{ g OC m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ and a few extreme values in the upper tail. *P. oceanica* showed a bimodal pattern, with two distinct peaks at 18 and $46 \text{ g OC m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, with 75 % of values below $50 \text{ g OC m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$. A two-

Fig. 1. Distribution of seagrass sites with available data on A) organic carbon (OC) accumulation rate (CAR, $\text{g C m}^{-2} \text{yr}^{-1}$) and B) soil OC stock in the top 25 cm (Mg C ha^{-1}). Circle size represents the magnitude of the reported value, and colors indicate species: *Posidonia oceanica* (green) and *Zostera marina* (eelgrass, brown). Background shading shows major seagrass geographic bioregions. C) Histograms of the compiled sediment CAR data for eelgrass and *P. oceanica* meadows. D) Compilation of sediment OC stocks reported for eelgrass and *P. oceanica* meadows.

sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test revealed a significant difference between the CAR distributions of eelgrass and *P. oceanica* ($D = 0.5431, p < 0.01$). The median of the compiled data showed eelgrass had half the measured net accumulation rate ($14.6 \text{ g OC m}^{-2} \text{yr}^{-1}$, n sites = 63) of *P. oceanica* ($30 \text{ g OC m}^{-2} \text{yr}^{-1}$, n sites = 39), a statistically significant difference (Wilcoxon rank-sum test: $W = 7874, p < 0.01$). The compiled data for eelgrass also gives a CAR of only about half that of a recent global compilation (Arias Ortiz, 2019) for all seagrass species of $24 \text{ g OC m}^{-2} \text{yr}^{-1}$ ($n = 115$). Moreover, the geometric mean eelgrass CAR ($9 \text{ g OC m}^{-2} \text{yr}^{-1}$) is only 21 % of the Tier 1 default emission factor of $43 \text{ g OC m}^{-2} \text{yr}^{-1}$ (geometric mean of $n = 6$), utilised in the Coastal Wetlands chapter of the 2013 Supplement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines (hereafter

Wetlands Supplement) for assessment of the carbon sink capacity during meadow restoration and derived from *P. oceanica* records. By contrast, the geometric mean *P. oceanica* CAR ($22 \text{ g OC m}^{-2} \text{yr}^{-1}$) is 51 % of the IPCC Tier 1 value.

3.2. Eelgrass sediment OC stocks

In the compiled data set (Fig. 1B,D) of OC stocks to 25 cm core lengths, the sediments in eelgrass meadows exhibited a narrow and right-skewed distribution of site-level OC stocks, which varied from 1.7 to $265.2 \text{ Mg OC ha}^{-1}$, with a median of $17.3 \text{ Mg OC ha}^{-1}$ ($n = 161$ sites). In contrast, *P. oceanica* meadows showed a broader range and greater

frequency of large OC stocks, with site-level OC stocks varying from 7.1 to 228.2 Mg OC ha⁻¹, and a median of 43.0 Mg OC ha⁻¹ ($n = 59$ sites). A two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test revealed a significant difference between the OC stocks distributions of eelgrass and *P. oceanica* ($D = 0.3919$, $p < 0.01$) and a Wilcoxon rank-sum test confirmed that median OC stocks were significantly higher in *P. oceanica* than in eelgrass meadows ($W = 1477$, $p < 0.01$). Our median OC stock for eelgrass is slightly lower than the median OC stocks in a recent global compilation for all seagrass species (19.3 Mg OC ha⁻¹, $n = 576$, Kennedy et al., 2022). The geometric mean eelgrass OC stock (16.9 Mg OC ha⁻¹) is about 62 % lower than the Tier 1 default OC stock (27 Mg OC ha⁻¹, $n = 89$, adjusted to top 25 cm) utilised in the 2013 IPCC Wetland Supplement for assessment of carbon dioxide emissions associated with extraction of sediment. For comparison, the geometric mean *P. oceanica* OC stock (47.8 Mg OC ha⁻¹) is about 77 % higher than the Tier 1 OC stock in the IPCC guidance.

3.3. Sediment OC stocks inside and outside eelgrass meadows

Across all sites, vegetated sediments had significantly higher OC stocks than unvegetated sediments, with a pooled mean difference of 4.33 Mg C ha⁻¹ (95 % CI: 1.32 to 7.33; $p = 0.0055$) under a random-effects model. Between-study heterogeneity was substantial ($\tau^2 = 129.11$, 95 % CI: 86.11 to 191.21; $I^2 = 99.5$ %), indicating considerable variability among studies (Fig. 2). Among the 65 sites analyzed, 26 showed higher OC stocks in vegetated sediments, 9 showed lower OC stocks, and 30 no significant difference. Subgroup analysis by stock thickness revealed that differences were greatest for medium (0–15 cm and up to 25 cm) and deep (0–25 cm and up to 50 cm) stocks (MD = 6.30 Mg C ha⁻¹, 95 % CI: 0.84 to 11.77; and MD = 6.11 Mg C ha⁻¹, 95 % CI: 0.19 to 12.03, respectively), while shallow stocks (0–3.5 cm and up to 15 cm) showed no detectable difference (MD = -0.64 Mg C ha⁻¹, 95 % CI: -3.40 to 2.12). The test for subgroup differences was significant ($Q = 8.62$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.013$), suggesting that stock thickness explained part of the observed heterogeneity (Fig. 2). Our compilation found only 6 paired values of vegetated and unvegetated sediments for *P. oceanica* meadows. While five of these sites showed higher OC stocks in vegetated sediments, the limited data prevented us from using a meta-analysis approach for comparison with the eelgrass dataset.

3.4. Accounting for allochthonous carbon

We used $\delta^{13}C_{\text{leaf}} - \delta^{13}C_{\text{sediment}}$ ($\Delta^{13}C$) values for eelgrass (Kindeberg et al., 2019) as an indication of the allochthonous contribution and found that the values vary from 1.3 to 15 ‰ (Fig. 3A) with a geometric mean of 8.2 ‰ ($n = 146$). The $\Delta^{13}C$ value for eelgrass is higher than that of a recent synthesis of global seagrass species $\Delta^{13}C$ values (median 7.4 ‰, $n = 500$, Ward et al., 2024) and much larger than for a persistent seagrass species such as *P. oceanica* (median 3.6 ‰, Kennedy et al., 2022), indicating a lower relative contribution of eelgrass organic matter to the sediment OC stock.

Commonly allochthonous OC contribution to the sediment has been assessed through stable isotopic composition ($\delta^{13}C$) of potential sources of OC, using Bayesian stable isotope mixing models (SIMMs). Studies using mixing models to apportion OC sources in eelgrass sediments show that eelgrass contributions range widely (Table 1), from 3 to 47 % in most temperate meadows to 60 to 94 % in a few cases, indicating that in some environmental settings eelgrass can dominate organic matter sources (Röhr et al., 2018). In contrast, *P. oceanica* contributions (based on only two studies covering 17 meadows) are more consistently high, ranging from 32 % to 74 % across Greek and Italian meadows (Table 1).

Alternatively, using the proxy provided to discount the residual recalcitrant allochthonous OC (Needelman et al., 2018), we find that for eelgrass only 27 %, 95 % CI [24 %, 33 %] of the sediment samples in this compilation would be considered to have a net positive OC value that could be used towards a carbon credit. For the remaining 73 %, the

MAOC deduction required was larger than the sediment OC (Fig. 3B). For *P. oceanica*, 69 %, 95 % CI [56 %, 80 %] of the sediment samples we calculated net positive OC values that could be used towards carbon credits (Fig. 3C).

4. Discussion

Compared to a persistent, spatially stable seagrass species our key findings for the dynamic eelgrass meadows are: 1) generally low sediment CAR and low OC stocks, 2) a higher allochthonous contribution, as indicated by $\Delta^{13}C$ and the estimated amount of recalcitrant allochthonous OC (MAOC), and 3) for most eelgrass meadows (~60 % of the sites analyzed), vegetated sediments did not have higher OC stocks than paired unvegetated sediments. We deliberate reasons for the lower CAR and limited OC storage capacity of eelgrass compared to *P. oceanica* and discuss the findings in the context of the central requirements for carbon market method requirements of additionality and permanence.

To be relevant in the context of carbon markets, projects must show *additionality*, i.e. it must be demonstrated that a restoration activity causes an additional reduction in net GHG emissions compared to the baseline or reference scenario (or business-as-usual scenario) without the project. The requirements to demonstrate additionality are: 1) that increases in OC stock or accumulation rate occur because of the project activities (e.g. restoration) and can be quantified, and 2) the capacity to track changes in the habitat extent and distinguish baseline conditions from those of the protected or restored meadow.

4.1. Additionality: measurable change in sediment organic carbon stock or accumulation rate

Assessing sediment OC accumulation rates in seagrass restoration projects can be challenging. Radionuclide techniques, such as ²¹⁰Pb dating, often face limitations due to the short duration of restoration projects (years rather than decades, Van Katwijk et al., 2016), and factors such as low accumulation rates, intense mixing of sediments, erosion or reworking of sediments (Arias-Ortiz et al., 2018b). In our compilation, 16 out of the 108 eelgrass meadows (15 %) showed null OC accumulation rates, indicating non-depositional areas, based on the low levels of excess ²¹⁰Pb. It is likely that studies with null accumulation rates remain under-reported, and the current number probably reflects an under-estimate of the frequency of occurrence of low rates of accumulation. However, in other sites, high levels of surface sediment mixing (e.g. due to bioturbation) may obscure low but positive accumulation rates using sediment core dating methods. Sediment accumulation, and hence, successful ²¹⁰Pb dating is rare in exposed, high-energy environments with low sediment retention. For example, Leiva-Dueñas et al. (2023) found no excess ²¹⁰Pb, therefore null accumulation, in five out of eight cores from eelgrass meadows. The remaining three sites, which accumulated sediment and were datable were those experiencing the lowest hydrodynamic exposure, assessed based on wave fetch. Similarly, Lafratta et al. (2020) successfully dated only one out of five cores from a *Posidonia australis* meadow in a bay with high fetch and wave energy. These findings underscore the difficulty of demonstrating additionality using ²¹⁰Pb dating in low-depositional, high-energy environments (Schaefer et al., 2025). To improve the likelihood of detecting change in sediment OC stocks (that would indicate accumulated sediment OC was additional with restoration activities), local knowledge and assessments of disturbance levels (e.g. natural, physical, sediment resuspension, bioturbation etc.) could guide project site selection. Opportunistic seagrass species, which colonize disturbed sites rapidly, may pose greater challenges for measuring restoration benefits in terms of OC accumulation rate or stock increases. However, these species also colonize more quiescent environments, where restoration projects that generate carbon credits may be more feasible.

The pronounced differences between our species-specific geometric means and the IPCC Tier 1 defaults underscore the limitations of using

Fig. 2. Forest plot of mean difference (MD) (and their 95 % CI and weights for individual trials) determined from the results of 84 observations comparing the sediment OC stock in vegetated and unvegetated areas. The final effect and the relative confidence interval are represented by the diamond and its lateral ends, respectively. The vertical continuous line indicates the no effect threshold. The effect and the respective confidence interval of each study and site are represented by the square and the horizontal line, respectively.

Fig. 3. A) Compilation of stable isotopic difference between paired values of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ surface sediment and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ leaf ($\Delta^{13}\text{C}$ ‰) in eelgrass meadows. Low values indicate large eelgrass contribution to sediment OC. Data retrieved from Kindeberg et al., 2019. B and C) Compilation of independently measured organic matter (OM) and organic carbon (OC) in eelgrass (Röhr et al., 2016, 2018) (plot B) and in *P. oceanica* sediments (Graversen et al., 2024) (plot C) used to calculate the reduction to account for mineral-associated organic carbon MAOC and expressed as a percentage of the total OC (Needelman et al., 2018). For data in the top left quadrant (pink), the reduction is larger than the measured OC. For data in the bottom right quadrant (green), the reduction is less than the measured OC. Red lines represent the fitted power function, while dashed grey lines indicate the upper and lower bounds of the 95 % confidence interval.

Table 1

Contribution of seagrass production to sediment OC in seagrass meadows, as estimated by mixing models in various studies. Values represent the percentage of total sediment OC derived from seagrass production.

Seagrass Species	Study location (number of locations)	Seagrass contribution to soil OC (%)	Source
Eelgrass	Temperate meadows (54)	3–94 %	Röhr et al., 2018
	East and Southeast Asia (4)	10–40 %	Miyajima et al., 2015
	Denmark (8)	33 ± 17 %	Leiva-Dueñas et al., 2023
	Virginia Coastal Bays (1, restored meadow)	< 40 %	Oreska et al., 2018
<i>Posidonia oceanica</i>	Poland (3)	40–45 %	Jankowska et al., 2016
	Italy (2)	32–36 %	Apostolaki et al., 2022
	Greece (15)	42 ± 11 % to 74 ± 4 % (average 60 ± 10 %)	Apostolaki et al., 2024

global benchmarks for carbon accounting as well as the need for updating the Tier 1 values and differentiating between large long-lived species and small, short-lived species. Tier 1 values, derived primarily from *P. oceanica* records, substantially overestimate CAR and OC stocks for eelgrass (by 79 % and 62 %, respectively). Such discrepancies can lead to biased GHG-inventories and misinformed climate and conservation policies.

The climate change mitigation potential of restored seagrass meadows relies on changes in both greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and OC accumulation relative to the situation without the restoration. Oreska et al. (2020) quantified the net OC accumulation (after deduction of allochthonous OC and GHG emissions) at levels as high as the IPCC Tier

1 level ($43 \text{ g OC m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) over the first three years of a restored eelgrass meadow. However, when the assessment period was extended to 15 years after the restoration, the CAR declined to $11.45 \text{ g OC m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, only 27 % of the Tier 1 value and nearer to the average CAR we compiled for eelgrass (Fig. 1A). This decline in CAR with time may reflect the lability of sediment OC and its potential for export and underscores the importance of assessing CARs over longer periods (Bradley et al., 2022). In the case of *P. oceanica* meadows in Greece (Apostolaki et al., 2024), where accumulation rates were determined over centuries, the OC depth profiles in most of the cores tended to have stable OC levels with depth due to the recalcitrant nature of the plant OC and there was little or no difference in the estimated OC accumulation rate over either 100 years or longer timescales.

Many factors affect autochthonous inputs to the sediment that contribute to the carbon accumulation and persistence of sediment OC stocks in seagrass meadows. Most seagrass traits leading to high contributions of autochthonous inputs are displayed by persistent meadows of slow growing species, such as *P. oceanica*, as opposed to those of faster growing species, such as eelgrass, commonly found in more dynamic environmental settings (Fig. 4). Traits such as gross primary production-to-respiration (P/R) ratio are, on average, ~ 1 for eelgrass, indicating little potential for long-term storage of autochthonous OC, while *P. oceanica* shows an average P/R ratio of 1.6, suggesting net autochthonous OC accumulation (Duarte et al., 2010; Berger et al., 2020). Additionally, the faster turnover of eelgrass below-ground biomass of 0.93 \% d^{-1} compared to 0.012 \% d^{-1} for *P. oceanica* (Duarte and Chiscano, 1999), further limits eelgrass's long-term storage of autochthonous OC in the sediment. Fast decomposition rates of eelgrass OC in many locations (Banta et al., 2004; Kristensen et al., 2025) can result in the accumulated carbon being predominantly allochthonous. Conversely, eelgrass autochthonous carbon can be preserved over longer timescales in settings of rapidly accumulating allochthonous OC through inhibition

Traits supporting autochthonous inputs to seagrass soils

Fig. 4. Major differences in traits displayed by persistent, spatially stable seagrass species epitomised by *P. oceanica* as opposed to those of eelgrass. Seagrass symbols by Tracey Saxby, Integration and Application Network, ian.umces.edu/media-library.

of mineralisation, especially of the more labile fractions. In Scandinavian settings though, the estimated autochthonous OC in eelgrass meadows would offer a limited contribution to climate change mitigation (Leiva-Dueñas et al., 2023). By contrast, *P. oceanica* rhizomes can remain intact for decades (e.g., Marbà and Duarte, 1997), forming reef-like structures called “matte”, that can extend several metres deep below the meadows and represent millennia of accretion (e.g., Boudouresque et al., 2016; Piñeiro-Juncal et al., 2025).

4.2. Additionality: baseline and areal extent

Our analysis reveals substantial heterogeneity in OC sediment stock differences between vegetated and unvegetated areas across eelgrass meadows. In most cases (~60 % of sites), vegetated sediments either did not differ significantly from bare sediments or had lower OC stocks than unvegetated areas (Fig. 2). This observation aligns with several possible explanations: 1) unvegetated sites may be adjacent to vegetated areas, receiving exported OC from nearby meadows; 2) unvegetated sites may have recently transitioned from vegetated states, retaining OC stocks from previous meadows; or 3) frequent shifts between vegetated and unvegetated states may hinder significant OC storage in dynamic meadows.

Extant eelgrass meadows often exhibit interannual and decadal variability in extent, which could be symptomatic of expected changes when eelgrass is restored at hydrodynamic sites, where meadows are often found. For example, Valle et al. (2013) reported that, on average, 12.9 % of vegetated areas turned bare annually, while 12.7 % of bare areas became vegetated each year over 14 years in the Ems estuary. Similarly, based on a series of monitoring data, Balsby et al. (2017) observed fjord-scale (total area about 55 km²) fluctuations in shallow (<2 m) eelgrass populations, with coverage ranging from <5 % to nearly 90 % over 27 years. Frederiksen et al. (2004a, 2004b) also documented rapid declines in five large Danish eelgrass meadows with reductions of about 60 % occurring in less than six years over a 40–50-year period. Recoveries occurred over similar time scales and documented that recolonization may take place relatively fast when suitable environmental conditions are present. However, the presence of human artifacts under extant eelgrass meadows indicate that the long-term permanence of these meadows can occur in some settings (e.g. Fischer, 2011; Krause-

Jensen et al., 2019).

The dynamic nature of eelgrass meadows increases the risk of incorrectly delimiting seagrass extent in the baseline scenario if they are designated solely based on the current habitat extent, as this may overlook historical meadow dynamics or recent transitions between vegetated and unvegetated states. For instance, currently unvegetated areas proposed as reference sites in Leiva-Dueñas et al. (2023) showed isotopic evidence of eelgrass-derived OC in deeper sediment layers, complicating the assessment of additional eelgrass sediment OC stocks compared to bare areas. Similarly, Schaefer et al. (2025) found that vegetated patches in dynamic eelgrass meadows only had higher OC stocks than bare areas if they remained vegetated for over half of the ~10-year assessment period. While detailed local baseline assessments can be costly, especially without historical data on eelgrass distribution or local environmental characteristics, accessible aerial and satellite imagery from recent decades can provide sufficient insight into meadow temporal dynamism and its impact on top sediment (10 to 30 cm depth) OC stocks (Schaefer et al., 2025).

A potential solution to define eelgrass extent in the baseline scenario could be assessments based on eelgrass spatial distribution data from several years, rather than relying solely on a snapshot of habitat extent. A spatial eelgrass extent model that integrates eelgrass areal data from multiple years (e.g. Valle et al., 2013), or the application of a seagrass habitat suitability model or a GIS tool to identify areas that would be suitable for eelgrass growth (e.g. Thom et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2023; Flindt et al., 2016), but which are currently unvegetated could ensure a more accurate identification of eelgrass reference or baseline scenarios. In the Virginia coastal bays, USA, the globally most successful eelgrass restoration project benefitted from clearly defined reference conditions. The entire area had been nearly devoid of eelgrass, due to the wasting disease, many years before the project was initiated, leaving surface sediments with almost no trace of eelgrass before the restoration (Oreska et al., 2020). This allowed the net effect of restoration on OC stocks and accumulation rates to be assessed by comparing the project and baseline conditions (Oreska et al., 2020). While similar conditions may exist in some settings, they may not be characteristic of the majority of potential eelgrass restoration sites.

The mis-attribution of a recently unvegetated (or sporadically vegetated) area within a project baseline extent is exacerbated by the

observation that many eelgrass meadows are patchy and do not have a spatially stable areal extent or consistently located boundaries (Balsby et al., 2017; Bull et al., 2012; de los Santos et al., 2019; Frederiksen et al., 2004a, 2004b; Schaefer et al., 2025; Valle et al., 2013). This dynamism makes it challenging to document net changes in extent or distinguish between areas that become sporadically unvegetated due to the natural variability of the eelgrass meadow and those that have remained enduringly bare. These challenges are exacerbated when baseline or project conditions are assessed over short-term periods, as they may fail to capture the natural variability and long-term trends necessary to accurately delimitate the baseline seagrass extent and restored eelgrass meadows.

In these instances of very dynamic changes in eelgrass extent, the project may attract a high percentage buffer, resulting in low financial returns. In carbon markets, the risk of unforeseen losses in carbon stock are covered through non-tradable buffer credits that can be drawn upon in the event of a reversal in carbon stocks in any individual project (IUCN, 2021). Under these conditions the emphasis would have to be on projects with large areal extent, where the removal of CO₂ due to the net accumulation of eelgrass OC may be small on a per m² basis, but at larger scales there would be a financial incentive to undertake the restoration.

In contrast, spatially stable seagrass like *Posidonia oceanica* exhibit much slower horizontal rhizome expansion rates—only a few centimeters per year—leading to gradual, century-scale spatial changes (e. g. Ardizzone et al., 2006; Díaz Almela et al., 2008). This stability contrasts sharply with the dynamic nature of eelgrass meadows, also reflected in their traits: faster specific shoot mortality and recruitment rates (Duarte et al., 2006), as well as potentially greater sexual reproduction efforts of eelgrass relative to *P. oceanica* (Inglis, 1999; Olesen et al., 2017). The greater temporal and spatial stability makes it easier to clearly distinguish between vegetated and bare areas and observe more pronounced differences in their sediment OC stocks. Recently unvegetated zones near *P. oceanica* meadows can be easily identified by the presence of ‘dead matte’ or macro debris in the sediment, which can persist for years or even decades, clearly distinguishing them from permanently unvegetated areas (e.g. Apostolaki et al., 2022).

4.3. Additionality: distinguishing autochthonous OC enhancement

Eelgrass carbon projects may require estimating and deducting carbon derived from allochthonous sources, unless that carbon would have been assumed to be released into the atmosphere in the baseline scenario (without the project). The allochthonous fraction of the OC to be deducted can be assessed through proxy analysis such as bulk stable carbon isotopic composition of the sediment OC (Ward et al., 2024) or estimation of the fraction of OC calculated from the MAOM in the sediment (Needelman et al., 2018).

Generally, stable carbon isotope analyses attribute less than 50 % of the bulk OC in eelgrass meadows to autochthonous sources, with the remainder from allochthonous inputs. The use of end-member mixing models assumes equal lability and contribution potential to the sediment OC and sometimes disregards other potential OC sources that may exist (Fulton et al., 2025; Ward et al., 2025). The model output is provided in the form of potential ranges of eelgrass contributions to the soil OC pool. These observations show some limitations in the practicability of using end-member mixing models to accurately quantify OC source contributions. A further limitation is that the export of OC outside the meadows is not accounted for in existing methodologies. It has been proposed that a broader approach taking a seascape perspective may address this limitation, although it becomes technically difficult to determine how much and where credit should be allocated (Dunk et al., 2025).

If using the proxy approach provided by VERRA to deduct the recalcitrant allochthonous OC (Needelman et al., 2018), our results indicate that most of the accumulated OC in eelgrass meadows would have to be deducted. A limitation of this proxy approach is that the

percent deduction is based on data derived from deep sea sediments (Blair and Aller, 2012). More recently, direct measurements of MAOC are being made after separation from particulate organic matter by size (POC ≤ 50–60 μm) or by density (POC ≤ 1.85 g cm⁻³), but most data is from tidal marsh and mangrove ecosystems where MAOC has been found to represent 53.5 ± 10.9 % of soil OC (Assavapanuvat et al., 2024). The origin of the OC that has been stabilised by association with soil minerals has been shown to be comprised of microbial products of decomposition of labile plant derived compounds (Assavapanuvat et al., 2024). Given the large uncertainties regarding the content, composition, origin, mobility and vulnerability to remineralisation of MAOC under natural and anthropogenically impacted conditions, further research is needed to assess factors driving variation in the recalcitrant fraction. This would refine the proxies used in market methodologies, helping to better understand the feasibility of eelgrass carbon projects.

4.4. Permanence

Another important requirement for carbon market projects is the permanence of the carbon storage. In the VERRA standard, GHG emission reductions or avoidance generated by actions need to be maintained over time scales of 100 years (Verra, 2023) so “permanence” is a relative term in this and other schemes.

Permanence is primarily influenced by anthropogenic threats and climate change impacts, and secondarily by seagrass life history (Turschwell et al., 2021). While *P. oceanica* is a protected species in the EU subjected to several direct regulations (EC Habitat Directive (92/43/EEC), Barcelona Convention, Bern Convention; Boudouresque et al., 2012) and a defined habitat in the Natura 2000 network, eelgrass lacks similar direct protection and can be designated as a feature of habitats such as “large shallow inlets and bays” in the EU, hence eelgrass may be more vulnerable to anthropogenic pressures. There is national-level protection for eelgrass in many countries (e.g. USA and UK), but the level of protection is variable throughout its globally distributed range. For any restoration project, particularly in the USA, the designated protection measures for the area commonly fail to address the threats that have led to restoration failure (Ward and Beheshti, 2023).

While restoration can be successful when direct human impacts are removed, indirect stressors such as disease and warming, including marine heatwaves, pose greater challenges. While no pandemics have been reported for *P. oceanica*, the 1930s “wasting disease”, caused by the protist *Labyrinthula zosterae*, devastated up to 90 % of all North Atlantic eelgrass (Sullivan et al., 2013). This disease persists today, with 11 % to 99 % of eelgrass plants infected in some North American meadows, increasing their vulnerability to human or climatic disturbances (Aoki et al., 2022). Rising ocean temperatures and marine heatwaves have also triggered severe diebacks for *Posidonia* sp. in Australia and the Mediterranean, and for eelgrass in the USA (Aoki et al., 2021; Hammer et al., 2018). It has been observed that susceptibility to warming and heat waves decreases along a gradient from slow-growing and long-living temperate species typical to faster-growing, tropical colonizing species, such as *Halodule*, *Halophila*, and *Syringodium* (Hatun et al., 2024). Seagrass meadows worldwide show a modal difference of 5 °C between present maximum temperatures and their thermal limit, with this difference being larger towards the polar distribution range of seagrasses compared to the equatorial range, which is more at risk to warming (Marbà et al., 2022). Understanding the effect of heatwaves on seagrass species is complex as ocean warming will not act as a single stressor but will be experienced through a range of stressors with varying impact on seagrass sediments (Aoki et al., 2021; Hatun et al., 2024). Longer term (2030 to 2100) modelling of *Z. muelleri* resilience to climate change by Hatun et al. (2024) predicted high variability in shoot densities due to time dependent loss and recovery, indicating that restoration pathways may not be linear with risk of carbon loss and halted carbon accumulation. These aspects will affect the overall restoration project outcomes. However, large-scale eelgrass restoration in Virginia demonstrated that

meadows can expand and provide net CAR despite patchy losses (Oreska et al., 2020). Similar restoration projects and modelling efforts are required before comparisons can be made against other seagrass species.

Seagrass life history strategies also influence their permanence to a lesser extent. Persistent species like *Posidonia* sp. show minimal variability in their trajectories, indicating high resilience due to strong physiological resistance, but often have limited recovery after disturbances (Turschwell et al., 2021; O'Brien et al., 2018). Resistance time reflects how long the species endures adverse conditions, while recovery rate indicates how fast it recovers after stress is removed. In contrast, opportunistic species like *Zostera* sp. exhibit greater variability, reflecting lower resilience arising from weaker resistance in response to disturbances and moderate recovery abilities, making them more vulnerable to threats like disrupted recruitment and hindered re-establishment (Turschwell et al., 2021; O'Brien et al., 2018). How these differences in life history influence seagrass carbon projects have yet to be established but could provide information to guide seagrass restoration project development.

4.5. Feasibility of successful restoration

Eelgrass is the most commonly restored seagrass species, representing 50 % of global seagrass restoration trials (Van Katwijk et al., 2016). However, for all seagrass species, only 37 % of trials were successful, and most are monitored for short periods, with, on average, 50 % of trials monitored for one year or less and only 27.5 % for over two years (Van Katwijk et al., 2016). The common lack of long-term data introduces uncertainty about whether restored seagrass beds will persist and maintain functionality. For restoration to be feasible, it must demonstrate, not only short-term success, but also resilience and sustainability over long periods, such as the large-scale restoration that has been achieved in Virginia coastal bays (Oreska et al., 2020). Other sites of smaller scale restoration activities and without the accumulated wealth of research data are often initiated in naturally dynamic areas where it would be relevant to initially evaluate the potential habitat, i.e. areas that can be potentially suitable for eelgrass growth under the prevalent environmental conditions (e.g. Bertelli et al., 2022). Subsequently, evaluation of the impact of restoration efforts on the eelgrass habitat distribution should include delimiting the habitat spatial extent by integrating multiple years both before and multiple years after implementing project actions. In contrast, *P. oceanica* has slower recovery rates and temporal dynamics, may require less frequent monitoring and thus lower monitoring costs to evaluate its long-term progress, further enhancing the feasibility of carbon projects restoring this species.

Using the global seagrass restoration dataset from van Katwijk et al. (2016), we calculated their semi-quantitative measure of restoration performance 'integrated success score' (ISS) for each seagrass genus. Genera were categorized by life history strategy (Kilminster et al., 2015), recovery rate, and resistance time (O'Brien et al., 2018). Fig. 5 reveals a U-shaped pattern, showing greater restoration success in genera with either fast recovery rates (e.g. *Halodule*) or long resistance times (e.g. *Posidonia*). *Posidonia* species demonstrate the highest restoration success, which, combined with their carbon accumulation rate, makes them a promising option for carbon credit projects (Comte et al., 2024). In contrast, *Zostera* displayed lower restoration performance compared to *Posidonia* (but similar to other genera), reflecting higher risks and reduced returns on investment compared to *Posidonia*. This, together with their lower CAR, makes eelgrass less suitable for such initiatives unless restoration techniques improve. However, eelgrass restoration projects could balance this by their potential for large scale projects (Oreska et al., 2020), wide global distribution (Green and Short, 2003), supportive national policies (Comte et al., 2024) and potentially lower vulnerability to climate stressors compared to *Posidonia* and other persistent genera. Eelgrass high-latitude distribution also suggests reduced vulnerability to climate warming compared to the more persistent seagrass species with an equatorial distribution range (Marbà

Fig. 5. Performance of seagrass restoration trials in relation to seagrass genera. The semi-quantitative integrated success score and its standard error of the mean were calculated from initial survival and long-term performance after initial survival. Bars are coloured according to seagrass life history strategy and sorted from lowest to highest recovery rate and highest to lowest resistance time. The numbers above the bars represent the total restoration trials with available data used to calculate the ISS for each genus (based on Van Katwijk et al., 2016).

et al., 2022).

Beyond the climate mitigation capacity associated with the restoration of seagrass meadows, there is a recognition of their role in provisioning of a wide range of other ecosystem services (Nordlund et al., 2016). Restoring and protecting seagrass meadows naturally increases or maintains benefits beyond climate change mitigation. Inclusion of these additional services can make a more effective argument for active management and, commercially, the stacking and bundling of ecosystem service credits is a possible mechanism to promote these activities (Torabi and Bekessy, 2015; Ward et al., 2025). These considerations are relevant for all seagrasses but hold special relevance for genera such as *Zostera*, given their more limited blue carbon capacity. While the communication of ecosystem service provision through restoration is relatively common, there is generally a lack of monetary quantification of restoration benefits. In addition, some ecosystem services are primarily socially or culturally valued by Indigenous communities and here governmental policy-driven initiatives could provide the necessary impetus for restoration (Douglas and Lohrer, 2024).

5. Conclusion

Eelgrass meadows generally have a low to moderate capacity for sediment OC accumulation compared to persistent, more stable seagrass species like *Posidonia oceanica* and eelgrass OC stocks are often similar to adjacent bare sediments and dominated by mineral-associated organic carbon (MOAC). These features, linked to eelgrass traits, their meadow dynamism, and geomorphic settings, pose challenges for voluntary market-based financing approaches for climate change mitigation. It has been shown that carbon credits can support eelgrass projects under certain circumstances, such as on the Virginia coast and potentially in other large restorable areas, but knowledge regarding the potential for large scale restoration opportunities are currently lacking. Beyond a better understanding of the factors needed to make projects more successful and efficient, the recovery of seagrass meadows is critical to benefit local communities through the many other ecosystem services they provide (e.g. biodiversity hotspots, coastal protection or nutrient filtering). Given the major anthropogenic and climate change pressures affecting seagrass meadows, it is essential to explore other incentives

such as non-market and public options for seagrass protection and restoration, based on their multiple benefits. Thus, protection and restoration should be a key priority in coastal zone management, contributing to buffering the interconnected biodiversity-, climate adaptation- and pollution crises and the vulnerability of coastal communities.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Hilary Kennedy: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Carmen Leiva-Dueñas:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Catherine E. Lovelock:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Dorte Krause-Jensen:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data have been uploaded to FigShare

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